

FORMATION OF ENGINEERING THINKING

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Abstract: In the article, the issue of forming the thinking of students studying technical education in higher educational institutions from general engineering sciences and ways of their integration are recommended.

Key words: philosophical views, opinion, intellect, logical thinking

Today we are in a historic period - our nation is living a peaceful life with noble and great goals, relying primarily on its own strength and capabilities, achieving great results in the way of building a democratic state and civil society. we live in the same era.

Taking our destiny into our own hands, relying on our ancient values, at the same time, taking into account the experience of developed countries, we are living with such noble aspirations, building the free, free and prosperous life that our people have been waiting for for centuries, Today, we all deeply understand that the international community recognized our achievements in this way - it was precisely independence that gave us all such opportunities.

In our country, special attention is paid to the education of the young generation. Work on creating the necessary conditions for boys and girls to receive modern education and grow up with high morals is being continued consistently. Today, the ability to analyze the philosophical views of our compatriot thinkers also serves as a basis for the development of national consciousness. National consciousness is of inestimable importance as a factor in the development of a broad outlook, which is necessary for society and every citizen. In this matter, the encyclopedist Farobi said that the spiritual and national heritage, spirits, that is, the

spirituality and consciousness of individuals, which have been collected by a certain people and the whole humanity, become nationalized and merge with each other. Despite the fact that the body of one generation disappears, their sources of consciousness are preserved, and during the period of the next generation, they adapt to the development of society, enrich with new opinions, and make a number of changes in the form of expression of national consciousness and ideas. In this way, the next generation will have the ability to do more perfect work as a person with a higher intelligence than the previous one. In the system of continuous development of consciousness, it moves from one direction to another, more perfect direction, becoming a dynamic process. Therefore, today's generation is developing national consciousness, embodying the spirit, ideas, and beliefs of people from the past. The current national consciousness is formed as a result of the completion of the similarities in the mind of the representatives of the previous generation, and the nationalism increases even more.

One of the virtues of Farobi's teaching is that he does not set nations against and above each other, but interprets them as an integral part of the entire humanity. So, Farobiy's ideas about society, theoretical concepts (orientations) are based on the ideas of nationalism and anti-racism, which are an actual issue at the present time, and at the same time, he expresses tolerance in the national consciousness. Because in Farobi's views, the concepts of nation and people are developed and reflected in the fact that they are objects (resources) that influence each other, and it can be seen that the word nation is also used in a secular sense.

The changes that are being implemented in the system of higher and secondary special education in our country at the moment, as well as in all fields, are aimed at all professors and teachers to bring students and young people to a higher level of knowledge, to educate them with a high moral quality, to communicate and study. , is setting very important and responsible tasks, such as improving their ability to

work, developing their ability to think independently and logically, and increasing their activity.

In order to successfully solve these tasks, it is necessary to have knowledge not only of the theoretical bases of humanitarian and socio-economic, mathematical and natural-scientific and specialized sciences in the field of technical education, but also to a certain extent general professional (technical mechanics) sciences. .

In the system of higher and secondary special education, the science of technical mechanics is considered one of the basic subjects of higher educational institutions in the direction of technical education, that is, other specialized subjects (basics of design of YESM, basics of machine design, YESM materials science, applied anthropology and biomechanics, design of technological processes, construction of TCH items, design of technological machines, production of TCH items and other sciences) provides a basis for learning.

Studying the science of technical mechanics has a positive effect on the development of logical thinking of students, mastering of general engineering sciences in the field of technical education. Technical and engineering competence (practical skills and competence) is an important issue for the professional training of students.

In order to form and develop deep and solid knowledge for students, it is of great importance to bring their knowledge into a single system, to be able to explain to them the inextricable connection with natural phenomena and technical production.

It helps to draw conclusions, construct objects or constructions (mechanisms or transmissions) and them, justify and calculate judgments, form and develop practical skills, bring concrete solutions, develop logical sensitivity.

The problems of summarizing and systematizing students' knowledge can be solved in the following ways:

1. Study and analysis of new material based on fundamental methodological laws of technical mechanics
2. Applying mechanical and mathematical laws and concepts to various objects and subjects, each section of the technical mechanics course (connections (relationships) between objects and subjects take different forms. Subjects is a source of object-oriented activity related to practical activity and knowledge, and objects are a source in the form of a viewed body or thing (construction).
3. Solving a system of problems that can be solved by creating single mathematical modules and calculation formulas.
4. Formation and development of a common opinion with the help of mathematical modeling in solving problems, i.e. in performing calculation-graphic work, course work and course projects ("Modeling" in the encyclopedic dictionary "Philosophy" is a scientific method based on direct learning. The main purpose of modeling is consists of studying objects and predicting future observations).
5. Solving model problems related to the formation of mechanical concepts and systematizing the performance of calculations.
6. It is necessary to create a systematic model of the teaching of technical mechanics, which is necessary for higher educational institutions in the field of technical education.
7. Effective use of innovative information technologies is required to generalize and systematize students' knowledge.

Information technology is a regulated and organized set of systems and applications that collect, process, store, express, distribute, transmit and deliver information to the consumer with the help of computers and telecommunications tools in order to find solutions to various problems. The use of new information technologies in education in the teaching of general professional subjects, like all subjects, provides an opportunity for students to acquire theoretical knowledge thoroughly and well, to develop their skills and abilities, and to strengthen them in

practice, an unconventional form of teaching based on various models, helps to use methods and tools.

Emphasizing the above, the implementation of the requirements requires students to think based on the laws of nature, to develop theoretical and practical skills, that is, their competence from the point of view of science.

Logical thinking is conscious, self-controlled thinking based on scientific theoretical foundations. According to Vygotsky, the absence of logic in thinking means the absence of independence and freedom in the process of thinking. Students develop independent thinking content based on logical thinking. Therefore, independent thinking is a mental activity that consists of solving problems and tasks in front of a person, relying on his knowledge and life experiences, with the help of various methods and tools, at the level of his intellectual capabilities.

The logical thinking process of students in higher educational institutions is influenced by the pedagogue's pedagogical skills and the subjects in the curriculum. They can be conditionally divided into two groups; subjects that form direct action skills and abilities, and more abstract subjects that compel mental, imaginative understanding. The more information available to students, the more varied and complementary, the more organized and logical their thinking becomes. Interdisciplinarity, their generalization, systematization, inductive, deductive approach play an important role in forming the logical thinking of future pedagogues. The high stage of the educational process is the development of independent knowledge skills and abilities based on the formation of students' internal need for knowledge. Application of modern pedagogical technologies in forming the logical thinking of students, comprehensive conceptual approach to educational content is important. Identifying the philosophical basis of learning such educational content, moving from reproductive mastery to the creative stage, connecting with life, directing mental activity to perform logical operations such as analysis, synthesis, creates a foundation for the birth of logical thought. Our

pedagogues' explanation of the educational process based on logic, problematization of the educational process, modularization and other interactive methods relying on the principles of scientificity, organicity, systematicity, and vitality are the priority in finding the content of students' logical thinking.

In the process of education, directing the pedagogues to creative knowledge creates a foundation for the formation of creative ideas in the mind of the individual, superficial knowledge is understood to be deprived of creative knowledge, and the formation of an independent conscious attitude is knowledge.

Therefore, in the professional formation of future pedagogues in higher educational institutions, we should consider raising the educational process from reproductive education to productive level as a social necessity. Therefore, it is impossible to form the independent free thinking of students without forming a critical thinking of logic in the formation of the profession of our pedagogues.

To have unexpected results and solutions by forming divergent thinking in students, branching out in different ways, spreading in different directions at the same time, creating many solution options.

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